

Local Government in Malaysia

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Local Responsibilities and Public Services

2.1. Local Responsibilities and Public Services in Malaysia: An Introduction

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Local authorities play a very important part in public life in Malaysia. Their responsibilities include planning and development control,²² public housing, parks and public places, public nuisances, garbage collection and disposal, a wide range of other environmental functions, local transport, including bus routes and taxi licensing, and roads other than highways. As is discussed in the report section on local finances, some services are provided via public-private partnerships, many of which are policy-orchestrated by the federal government.

Housing and planning are closely interrelated and form the most significant area of government activity that local governments control. In a rapidly developing and rapidly urbanizing country these functions are some of the most important that are carried out at any level of government. They are counter-balanced by the environmental powers of local authorities, which attempt to minimize the adverse effects of rapid development. These include powers over water pollution, public nuisances, transport and markets, as well as general planning powers (see section 6 below).

As has been noted above, Malaysia is an ethnically divided country, and, while Malays are in a large majority in rural areas, urban areas are generally more evenly divided demographically between members of Malay and non-Malay (mainly Chinese and Indian) communities. Allocation of housing and profit-making opportunities (in respect of development projects and public contracts) are sensitive issues, and one reason for the continuing refusal to reintroduce local elections is the possibility of political exploitation of inter-ethnic issues at the local level. For example, local authorities are responsible for business licensing and allocation of permits for establishing places of worship. The role of local authorities in the period of the pandemic (March 2020 to date) has proved to be critical in terms of coordination of local government with state and federal government powers via local powers over infectious diseases and business licensing. However, such coordination has often proved to be defective in practice.

Under the dominance of the Barisan Nasional (BN) government (1957-2018) demands for reintroducing local government elections were easily suppressed. Since 2018 political fragmentation, accompanied by the need to deal with the pandemic, has hampered deep attention to policy questions such as the future of local government. At the time of writing the stability of the present PN Malaysian government, having a razor-thin parliamentary majority,

²² For some more detail, see report section 6 on people's participation in local decision-making.

is very much in doubt, and the pandemic obstructs the holding of general elections. The system of local government is undoubtedly in need of reform, but any concerted reform process seems a very remote possibility at the present time.

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